

A CONDUCTIVE EXPRESSION TO Zeta(three)

Elizabeth ZHOU and Ming ZHOU

ABSTRACT. We acquire an interesting expression of the Riemann $\zeta(3)$ in terms of π^2 , $\zeta(3) = \pi^2[1 - \gamma + \frac{2}{3}\ln(\frac{2}{\pi}) + \epsilon(n)]$, with a seemingly irrational coefficient. $[1 - \gamma + \frac{2}{3}\ln(\frac{2}{\pi})]$, its main part, includes $\ln 2$, $\ln \pi$ and γ , where γ is the Euler–Mascheroni constant.

1 Introduction

Leonhard Euler solved the famous Basel problem $\zeta(2) = \pi^2/6$ in 1734, and then established the beautiful formula $\zeta(k) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} 1/n^k$ in terms of π^k when k is even. However, finding a formula for the sum $\zeta(3) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} 1/n^3$, or more generally $\zeta(k) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} 1/n^k$ with an odd k , became a famous unresolved question. Since then, the exact expressions of Riemann ζ (odd) have been an area of interest. Notwithstanding Apéry proved that $\zeta(3)$ is irrational in 1978. Are there exact sums to the Riemann ζ (odd)? If so, what should their closed expressions look like?

In this paper, we obtain an expression $\pi^2[1 - \gamma + \frac{2}{3}\ln(\frac{2}{\pi}) + \epsilon(n)]$ for $\zeta(3) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} 1/n^3$ using several elementary methods: complex analysis, Taylor expansion, and numerical computation and comparison.

2 A Pair of Equations

For the complex series below,

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{z^n}{n}, \quad n \in +\mathbb{Z} \text{ and } z \in \mathbb{C}, \quad (1)$$

it is easy to know that the radius of convergence of this series is 1, so its sum is an Entire Function in the unit disk of complex plane [1]. Let us set

$$f(z) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{z^n}{n},$$

and its derivative

$$f'(z) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} z^{n-1} = \frac{1}{1-z},$$

hence,

$$f(z) = -\ln(1 - z),$$

namely,

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{z^n}{n} = -\ln(1 - z), \quad |z| < 1.$$

On the circle $|z| = 1$, the series is not absolutely convergent because the Harmonic Series $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} 1/n$ diverges. By Abel's Theorem for power series, when

$$z = e^{i 2\pi x}, \quad (0 < x < 1) \mid x \in \mathbb{R},$$

(1) becomes as

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{e^{i 2\pi n x}}{n} &= -\ln(1 - e^{i 2\pi x}) \\ &= -\ln|(1 - e^{i 2\pi x})| - i \arg(1 - e^{i 2\pi x}). \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The Unit Disk of Complex Plane

The image above shows the relationship

$$|(1 - e^{i 2\pi x})| = 2 \sin \frac{2\pi x}{2},$$

$$\arg(1 - e^{i 2\pi x}) = -\theta,$$

where

$$\theta = \frac{\pi - 2\pi x}{2}.$$

This is it, (2) becomes as

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{e^{i 2\pi n x}}{n} = -\ln(1 - e^{i 2\pi x}) = -\ln(2 \sin \pi x) - i \frac{\pi - 2\pi x}{2}.$$

Two interesting and concise equations have been done by comparing the real part and

the imaginary part of both sides of the equation above. Notably, they are two series associated with the *sine* and the *cosine* functions.

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\sin(2\pi n x)}{n} = \frac{\pi - 2\pi x}{2}, \quad (3)$$

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\cos(2\pi n x)}{n} = -\ln(2 \sin \pi x). \quad (4)$$

Note: by substituting $x=1/4$ and $x=1/2$ into (3) and (4) respectively, the two equations above are found to be true without any other numbers such as integrating constants.

Concurrently, two famous results are easily revealed:

For (3),

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\sin(2\pi n x)}{n} \Big|_{x=\frac{1}{4}} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{2n-1} = \frac{\pi - 2\pi x}{2} \Big|_{x=\frac{1}{4}},$$

namely,

$$1 - \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{5} - \frac{1}{7} + \frac{1}{9} - \frac{1}{11} + \dots = \frac{\pi}{4},$$

which is the **Leibniz formula** for π .

For (4),

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\cos(2\pi n x)}{n} \Big|_{x=\frac{1}{2}} = -\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n} = -\ln(2 \sin \pi x) \Big|_{x=\frac{1}{2}},$$

namely,

$$1 - \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3} - \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{5} - \frac{1}{6} + \dots = \ln 2,$$

which is the Alternating Harmonic Series.

Moreover, integrating both sides of (3) with respect to x gives

$$\begin{aligned} \int \left[\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\sin(2\pi n x)}{n} \right] dx &= \int \frac{\pi - 2\pi x}{2} dx, \\ \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \int \frac{\sin(2\pi n x)}{(2\pi n)n} d(2\pi n x) &= \frac{\pi}{2}x - \frac{\pi}{2}x^2 - C_1, \\ \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{-\cos(2\pi n x)}{(2\pi n)n} &= \frac{\pi}{2}x - \frac{\pi}{2}x^2 - C_1, \\ \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\cos(2\pi n x)}{n^2} &= \pi^2 x^2 - \pi^2 x + C_1, \end{aligned}$$

where C_1 is a constant.

When inserting $x=1/4$ and $x=1/2$ to the above equation respectively, two concrete equations are given below

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\cos(2\pi n x)}{n^2} \Big|_{x=\frac{1}{4}} &= \pi^2 x^2 - \pi^2 x + C_1 \Big|_{x=\frac{1}{4}}, \\
\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\cos\left(n\frac{\pi}{2}\right)}{n^2} &= \pi^2 \left(\frac{1}{4}\right)^2 - \pi^2 \left(\frac{1}{4}\right) + C_1, \\
\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{(2n)^2} &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{-1}{2^2} \left(\frac{1}{n^2} - 2\frac{1}{(2n)^2}\right) = \frac{-1}{2^3} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^2} = -\frac{3}{16}\pi^2 + C_1, \quad (5)
\end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\cos(2\pi n x)}{n^2} \Big|_{x=\frac{1}{2}} &= \pi^2 x^2 - \pi^2 x + C_1 \Big|_{x=\frac{1}{2}}, \\
\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\cos(n\pi)}{n^2} &= \pi^2 x \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^2 - \pi^2 \left(\frac{1}{2}\right) + C_1, \\
\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{n^2} &= -\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{n^2} - 2\frac{1}{(2n)^2}\right) = \frac{-1}{2} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^2} = -\frac{\pi^2}{4} + C_1. \quad (6)
\end{aligned}$$

Solving (5) and (6), shows that

$$\zeta(2) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^2} = C_1 = \frac{\pi^2}{6}.$$

This result is known as the Basel problem $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (1/n^2) = \pi^2/6$, which was first posed by Pietro Mengoli in 1650 and solved by L. Euler in 1734. This means that the constant of the first integration of (3) also is Euler's solution for $\zeta(2)$.

Finally (3) can be rewritten as

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\cos(2\pi n x)}{n^2} = \pi^2 \left(x^2 - x + \frac{1}{6}\right).$$

In this way, many of the sums of the relevant series in Euler's book [2] can be derived from this expression.

3 A Expression for $\zeta(3)$

Equation (4) looks like a tidy formula, but when the logarithmic composite function on the right side is integrated, it is not as easy to work with as equation (3) because its antiderivative function with the form of elementary functions does not exist. This is really a tricky problem. But we are interested in doing something on (4).

Setting the right side of (4) as $R(x)$, namely,

$$R(x) = -\ln(2 \sin \pi x) = -\ln 2 - \ln[1 + (\sin \pi x - 1)].$$

And the Taylor series for sine and logarithmic functions in the above equation are

respectively,

$$\begin{aligned}\sin \pi x &= \left(\frac{\pi x}{2} + \frac{\pi x}{2}\right) - \frac{(\pi x)^3}{3!} + \frac{(\pi x)^5}{5!} - \frac{(\pi x)^7}{7!} + \frac{(\pi x)^9}{9!} - \frac{(\pi x)^{11}}{11!} + \dots, \\ \ln[1 + (\sin \pi x - 1)] &= (\sin \pi x - 1) - \frac{(\sin \pi x - 1)^2}{2} + \frac{(\sin \pi x - 1)^3}{3} \\ &\quad - \frac{(\sin \pi x - 1)^4}{4} + \frac{(\sin \pi x - 1)^5}{5} - \frac{(\sin \pi x - 1)^6}{6} + \dots.\end{aligned}$$

Thus, we get the following expression in $R(x)$,

$$\begin{aligned}\ln[1 + (\sin \pi x - 1)] &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\left[-1 + \left(\frac{\pi x}{2} + \frac{\pi x}{2}\right) - \frac{(\pi x)^3}{3!} + \frac{(\pi x)^5}{5!} - \frac{(\pi x)^7}{7!} + \dots\right]^n}{(-1)^{n-1} n} \\ &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\left[\left(\frac{\pi x}{2} - 1\right) + \frac{\pi x}{2} - \frac{(\pi x)^3}{3!} + \frac{(\pi x)^5}{5!} - \frac{(\pi x)^7}{7!} + \dots\right]^n}{(-1)^{n-1} n}.\end{aligned}$$

Taking the first five terms in $\sin \pi x$ and the first six terms in $\ln[1 + (\sin \pi x - 1)]$, and then simplifying the above equation, we get

$$\begin{aligned}\ln[1 + (\sin \pi x - 1)] &= \ln\left(\frac{\pi x}{2}\right) + 3(\pi x) - \frac{45(\pi x)^2}{8} + \frac{28(\pi x)^3}{6} \\ &\quad - \frac{65(\pi x)^4}{64} - \frac{513(\pi x)^5}{240} + \frac{769(\pi x)^6}{384} - \frac{703(\pi x)^7}{2520} + \dots.\end{aligned}$$

For the sake of convenience, we set

$$\begin{aligned}E_1(x) &= 3(\pi x) - \frac{45(\pi x)^2}{8} + \frac{28(\pi x)^3}{6} - \frac{65(\pi x)^4}{64} \\ &\quad - \frac{513(\pi x)^5}{240} + \frac{769(\pi x)^6}{384} - \frac{703(\pi x)^7}{2520} + \dots.\end{aligned}$$

Note: there exists no regularity for the coefficients of the terms in $E_1(x)$ with respect to x .

Substituting the last two equations into (4) yields

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\cos(2\pi n x)}{n} = R(x) = -\ln(\pi x) - E_1(x).$$

Integrating both sides of the equation above twice, we get

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\cos(2\pi n x)}{(2\pi n)^2 n} = \frac{3x^2}{4} - \frac{x^2 \ln(\pi x)}{2} - \iint E_1(x) dx + C_2,$$

where C_2 is a constant, and then,

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\cos(2\pi n x)}{n^3} = \pi^2 [2x^2 \ln(\pi x) - 3x^2] + 4\pi^2 \iint E_1(x) dx + C_2.$$

Substituting $x=1/2$ into the above equation gives

$$\begin{aligned}\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\cos(\pi n)}{n^3} &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{n^3} = -\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{1}{n^3} - \frac{2}{(2n)^3} \right] = -\frac{3}{4} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^3} \\ &= \pi^2 \left[2 \left(\frac{1}{2} \right)^2 \ln \left(\pi \frac{1}{2} \right) - 3 \left(\frac{1}{2} \right)^2 \right] + 4\pi^2 \iint E_1(x) dx + C_2,\end{aligned}$$

then,

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^3} = \left(\frac{-4}{3} \right) \left\{ \pi^2 \left[\frac{1}{2} \ln \left(\frac{\pi}{2} \right) - \frac{3}{4} \right] + 4\pi^2 \iint E_1(x) dx + C_2 \right\},$$

and then,

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^3} = \pi^2 \left[1 - \frac{2}{3} \ln \left(\frac{\pi}{2} \right) \right] - \frac{16}{3} \pi^2 \iint E_1(x) dx + C_2,$$

namely,

$$\begin{aligned}\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^3} &= \pi^2 \left[1 + \frac{2}{3} \ln \left(\frac{2}{\pi} \right) \right] + E_3(x), \\ \zeta(3) &= \pi^2 \left[1 + \frac{2}{3} \ln \left(\frac{2}{\pi} \right) \right] + E_3(x),\end{aligned}\tag{7}$$

where $E_3(x)$ is introduced into the above equation, as

$$E_3(x) = -\frac{16}{3} \pi^2 \iint E_1(x) dx + C_2.$$

Due to the complexity and irregularity of the infinite power series $E_1(x)$, $E_3(x)$ is even more elusive. That means $E_3(x)$ cannot be directly used for calculation and analysis. Coincidentally, through numerically calculating (5), we find that the value of $E_3(x)/\pi^2$ is approximately equal to -0.577101349, the digits of which are very close to those of Euler's constant, $\gamma = 0.5772156649 \dots$.

Therefore, we rewrite (5) as

$$\zeta(3) = \pi^2 \left[1 - \gamma + \frac{2}{3} \ln \left(\frac{2}{\pi} \right) + \varepsilon(n) \right],\tag{8}$$

where $\varepsilon(n)$ is named an analytic constant or error, specifically

$$\varepsilon(n) = -\frac{16}{3} \iint E_1(x) dx + C_2.$$

It is clear that $\varepsilon(n)$, as well as $E_3(x)$, cannot be directly used for calculation and analysis.

In our studies, Equation 4 is sometimes written in the following form,

$$\zeta(3) = \pi^2 \mathcal{M}(\varepsilon),\tag{9}$$

where, $\mathcal{M}(\varepsilon)$ is called the coefficient of π^2 , as

$$\mathcal{M}(\varepsilon) = \left[1 - \gamma + \frac{2}{3} \ln \left(\frac{2}{\pi} \right) + \varepsilon(n) \right].$$

4 Conclusions

Although the expression (8) and (9) is not a closed form for $\zeta(3)$, we can further understand $\zeta(3)$ from a new perspective:

- a) In equation (8), $\zeta(3)$ is not expressed in terms of π cubed, but in terms of π squared. And $\mathcal{M}(\varepsilon)$, the coefficient of π^2 , is seeming irrational. They are completely different from $\zeta(2)$ or all Riemann zeta functions with even numbers;
- b) If formulae of other Riemann zeta functions $\zeta(k) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} 1/n^k$ with odd k exist, do they all have the same form as $\zeta(3)$, namely, in terms of π^{k-1} rather than π^k and with irrational coefficients of π^{k-1} ?
- c) If formulae of $\zeta(3)$ exist, can $\varepsilon(n)$ be expressed in closed form? That is one of our curious questions. For reference, $\varepsilon(n) \cong 6.463 \times 10^{-6}$ for $\zeta(3)$.

References

- [1] Emil G. Milewski: *The Complex Variables Problem Solver*, Research and Education Association, 1989.
- [2] Leonhard Euler: *Introduction to Analysis of Infinite*, Springer-Verlag NY Inc., 1988.

Elizabeth ZHOU, UC Berkeley
Ming ZHOU, Tianjin Vico Co., Ltd.

elizzhou@berkeley.edu
pdebox@yahoo.com